

Validating the Weiskopf 3x3 Data Quality Assessment Framework

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That Doesn't Seem Right...

- 17,000 pregnant British men
- Married and divorced 6-year olds
- Physical examinations performed on the walking dead

Electronic Health Record Data

- 2009 Health Information Technology for Economic and Clinical Health Act:
 - Large-scale deployment of electronic health records
 - Improved health-related decision making and patient outcomes
 - Increased provider and patient access to data
 - Violated assumptions of data quality (DQ)

Data Quality

- Importance is clear
- Definition is less clear

Data Quality – Divided We Stand

- Chan et al., 2010 reviewed 35 studies and found significant disagreement regarding assessed DQ dimensions
 - 66% accuracy, 57% completeness, 23% data comparability
- Weiskopf and Wang (2013) conducted a meta-analysis and identified over 20 unique DQ dimensions

Weiskopf 3x3 DQ Assessment Framework

- 3 DQ dimensions

Complete	Correct	Current
Is a truth about a patient present?	Is an element that is present true?	Is an element a relevant representation of a patient state at a given point in time?

- 3 dimensions of data

Weiskopf 3x3 DQ Assessment Framework

	A: COMPLETE	B: CORRECT	C: CURRENT
1: PATIENT	<p>Are there sufficient observations for a variable of interest?</p> <p><i>Example: Do I have enough observations with complete visit information?</i></p>		
2: VARIABLES			
3: TIME			<p>Were data recorded with desired regularity over time?</p> <p><i>Example: What is the average time between patient visits?</i></p>

Framework lacks formal quantitative validation!

Methods

Three-Step Framework Validation:

1. Develop operational measures (i.e., descriptive statistics and visualizations)
2. Implement measures against the Observational Medical Outcomes Partnership (OMOP) common data model
3. Field-test measures using Children's Hospital Colorado (CHCO) data collected between 2010-2014

Results

- Final dataset included:
 - 560,451 patients
 - 769,648 procedures
 - 3,350,801 visits
 - 11,617,870 diagnoses
- Operational measures and visualizations identified for 8 of the 9 cells
- Applying measures and visualizations identified several DQ anomalies

NOTE: Visualizing large sample sizes required y-axis log-transformation; actual counts provided and y-axis removed for accurate data representation

Correct

Patient	Variable	Time
Is the distribution of values across patients plausible?	Is there concordance between variables?	Is the progression of data over time plausible?

Patient Year of Birth Distribution

Illustrates all patients were born between 1909 and 2014
($M=2003.36$, $SD=8.20$).

DQ Finding:
There were 510 (0.10%) patients born prior to 1940; inconsistent with CHCO records.

Correct

Patient	Variable	Time
Is the distribution of values across patients plausible?	Is there concordance between variables?	Is the progression of data over time plausible?

Illustrates the temporal ordering of visit occurrence observations by place of service.

DQ Finding:
The Ambulatory Surgery, Inpatient, and Outpatient Departments had 598 (0.02%) erroneous observations.

Correct

Patient	Variable	Time
Is the distribution of values across patients plausible?	Is there concordance between variables?	Is the progression of data over time plausible?

Emergency Department Monthly Visits (2010-2014)

Illustrates the trends in monthly visits to the ER by year (2010-2014).

DQ Finding:
Counts of December ER visits were significantly lower in both 2010 and 2011 ($p < .0001$); consistent with state influenza records.

Conclusions

- Understanding the usability of EHR data is of paramount importance
- Need analysis-driven validation efforts utilizing alternative data sources (i.e., adult ER, claims data)
- Framework-based applications and tool development is crucial for adoptability (i.e., automated scripts and/or DQ R package)

Limitations

- The Current Variable cell of the framework requires operational measure development
- Very clean CHCO data

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